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Technology Transfer & Valorisation

Semiconductor Manufacturing in Europe

Report on the State-of-the-Art

Aidan Marca, Fabio Ugolini

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10.5281/zenodo.8172048

info@innova-eu.net

+39 06 4004 0358

Via Giacomo Peroni, 386,
00131 Rome - Italy

www.innova-eu.net

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Executive Summary

Overview

This document seeks to provide a comprehensive overview of semiconductor manufacturing in Europe. Semiconductor manufacturing is a critical industry that plays a key role in powering various technological advancements in our world today. Many industries are becoming increasingly reliant on semiconductor technology such as automotive, artificial intelligence, and quantum computing. This report will explore the European Union's response to the recent supply chain shortage of semiconductors, their share in the semiconductor market, the different types of semiconductors produced, their main applications, sourcing of raw materials, and key players in the region.

The Problem

The main issue that Europe, among other countries, faces regarding semiconductor production is its interdependencies on other countries for materials and processes due to the complex global semiconductor value chain that exists in the market. In other words, a semiconductor chip has to pass through a multistep production process involving multiple countries and materials for it to reach its final stage, ready for implementation to a piece of technology. The market share of semiconductors is therefore dictated by how many steps of the process a country controls, and how well countries can use the semiconductor value chain to their advantage.

Key Findings

Although Europe only controls about 10% of the global semiconductor production process, they do have access to important resources that other countries are highly dependent on for production. For example, The Netherlands' ASML is the biggest semiconductor company in Europe and the largest producer of semiconductor fabrication machines capable of manufacturing semiconductor chips smaller than 7 nanometers. Europe also produces a third of global high-purity silicon through the German company Wacker Chemie. Evidently, these materials are essential to semiconductor production and give Europe a unique advantage over other countries within the global semiconductor market.

The Opportunity

The main opportunity for Europe is to leverage its advantages within the market to get access to other vital materials from countries dependent on EU exports, which will ultimately improve its competitiveness. Given the fact that a third of global high-purity silicon (the main metal used in wafer production) exports come from Germany, it is in the EU's best interest to leverage this resource and use it to its advantage when making trade deals with other countries for semiconductor equipment. Europe also has the opportunity to increase the production of semiconductor chips smaller than 7 nanometers by establishing more fabrication plants in Europe to encourage European producers of semiconductor machines such as ASML to sell to a European customer base.

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Introduction

This document provides a comprehensive summary of semiconductor manufacturing in Europe. Semiconductor manufacturing is a critical industry that plays a key role in powering various technological advancements. This report will cover the European Union's contributions to the global semiconductor market, including Europe's response to the recent supply chain shortage of semiconductors, as well as the different types of semiconductors produced, their main applications, sourcing of raw materials, market size, key players in the region, and a recommendation.

Types of Semiconductors

Semiconductors are devices that have an electrical conductivity value falling between a conductor, such as copper, and an insulator, such as glass. They typically consist of materials like silicon, germanium, and gallium for their functioning in electronic devices. Semiconductor chips are crucial components of some of the world's newest technologies, including electric vehicles, artificial intelligence, quantum computing, and the Internet of Things. Semiconductors can be separated into two main categories: **Optoelectronics, Sensors, and Discrete Semiconductors (OSDs)**, and **Integrated Circuits (ICs)** which include Logic, Memory, Micro, and Analog.

Figure 1 explains the relationship between these various categories of semiconductors, and after a brief description.

Figure 2 shows Europe's share of the market based on each kind of semiconductor.

Figure 1: Types of Semiconductors

1. *Logic circuits:* Logic chips are crucial components used in electronic systems, that help enable more complex operations such as signal processing, data manipulation, and control. Logic circuits are typically used for the function of advanced computer memory and complete microprocessors by adding numbers or decoding an input string into an informative output. Logic circuits are used in technologies such as smartphones and tablets, or within memory devices.
2. *Memory Chips:* Memory chips are used to store data in electronic devices. The two main types of memory chips include dynamic random-access memory (DRAM) and non-volatile storage technology (NAND). DRAM memory chips are used for data or program code needed by a computer processor to function in devices such as personal computers, workstations, and servers. NAND memory chips are used to save data as blocks and rely on electric circuits to store data in devices such as MP3 players, digital cameras, and USB flash drives.
3. *Microprocessors and Microcontrollers:* Microprocessors and microcontrollers are central processing units of computers that are responsible for processing information and performing all the basic functions of a

computer. These microchips are used in everything from keyboard controllers to complex industrial controllers.

4. *Analog*: Analog integrated circuits such as operational amplifiers, power management circuits, and sensors change analog data like voice recordings into digital data. Analog integrated circuits play important roles in the development of automotive, industrial, and consumer electronics.
5. *Optoelectronics*: Optoelectronic devices involve the interaction of light and electricity, enabling applications such as optical communication, displays, and sensors. European semiconductor manufacturers produce optoelectronic components like light-emitting diodes (LEDs), laser diodes, and photodetectors.
6. *Sensors*: Sensors are electronic devices used to interpret analog or electric signals including temperature, sound, motion, smell, and transmit a corresponding electronic signal. Sensor semiconductors are used in navigation systems, optical devices, and motion sensors, as well as health monitors.
7. *Discrete Semiconductors*: Discrete Semiconductors are specified to perform an elementary function and can't be divided up into different functions. Examples of discrete semiconductors include diodes, transistors, and rectifiers.

Figure 2: Europe's Market Share by Category, 2021

Source: WSTS [Historical Billings Report](#), [RaboResearch](#), (2021)

EU Market

Market Size

Semiconductor production is knowledge and capital-intensive and is expected to grow given its importance to the development of products such as supercomputers, quantum computing, automated cars, the internet of things, AI, and applications in space and defense. Chips will therefore continue to be economically and strategically important to the expansion of computing capacities and innovation in general, moving forward. Europe is currently responsible for about 10% of the global semiconductor market, (**Figure 3**) which is expected to double from \$550 million currently to over \$1 trillion by 2030 (Van Wieringen, 2022). It is therefore essential for the EU to reinforce its technological capabilities in the semiconductor market to strengthen future strategic autonomy, digital sovereignty, and global competitiveness.

Figure 3: Europe VS Competitors by Market Cap

Source: WSTS [Historical Billings Report](#), McKinsey's projected yearly growth (2022).

Semiconductor Value Chain

The semiconductor production process can be broken down into 4 main steps which highlight the complexity of the process and the extent of interdependency among nations for the production of these vital semiconductor chips. **Step 1** of the process is the production of wafers, which are the base forms of semiconductors. Wafer production requires wafer manufacturing equipment that uses raw materials such as silicon and semiconductor metals as well as inputs including photographic sheets, chemicals, and gasses. Once the wafer is completed, **Step 2** begins, in which additional inputs such as sheets, mirrors, and lenses are added and processed by equipment such as fans and heating units to transform the wafer into a semiconductor. Once the semiconductor is completed, **Step 3** begins, in which semiconductors are then processed by tubes and transistors into intermediate electronics. **Step 4** involves incorporating the intermediate electronics into the final products they are used for such as calculating machines, data processors, etc. Throughout this process, the various materials and machinery necessary for production are imported and exported across different countries to make complete semiconductor production possible (Kan Ji, 2023). The EU's main imports and exports are explained below, along with **Figure 4** and **Figure 5** which visualize them on a global scale, corresponding to the steps involved in the process.

Imports

The European Union is a net importer of discrete semiconductors such as diodes, transistors, and similar semiconductor devices from China, which contributes to 50% of EU imports in this category. Taiwan is the second largest exporter of similar semiconductor devices, transistors, and diodes to the EU, followed by Japan for the other products included in the category. When it comes to integrated circuits (ICs), which include processors, D-rams, multi-combinational memories, and amplifiers, Taiwan is the largest exporter to the EU, accounting for around 20% of EU imports in this category. The EU is also a net importer of metals for the production of chips such as silicon, beryllium, chromium, vanadium, germanium, and gallium. They source these metals from China, Russia, and The United States, jointly accounting for 68% of imports in this category (Ciani, 2022).

Figure 4: Shares of imported goods in the semiconductor supply chain

Source: BACI (2021), [RaboResearch](#)

Exports

Although the European Union imports most of their semiconductor components, they are a large net exporter of machines for the production of semiconductors. These machines are exported mainly to countries leading in chip production including China, Taiwan, South Korea, and The United States. Taiwan is the main importer of these machines for semiconductors and integrated circuits (ICs) production, whereas China is the main importer of these machines for the production of boules and wafers. Boules are the base starting materials for semiconductor production, usually consisting of silicon. Wafers are thin, disc-shaped materials that typically consist of crystalline silicon and are used in the fabrication of integrated circuits.

Another important export The European Union has in the global semiconductor value chain is silicon. Germany accounts for a third of global high-purity silicon exports mainly from the company Wacker Chemie, amounting to over \$1 billion of the market share as the top net exporter. The main importer of this essential semiconductor material is China, which imports around 70% of German silicon (Kan Ji, 2023). These companies' expertise in supplying this crucial semiconductor component to key players within the global semiconductor market contributes to the overall strength and competitiveness of Europe's semiconductor industry.

Figure 5: Shares of exported goods in the semiconductor supply chain

Source: BACI (2021), RaboResearch

Europe also has innovative research facilities such as Imec in Belgium, Leti in France, and Fraunhofer in Germany, which focus on supplying devices to the automotive, aerospace, and industrial automation industries (Hollinger, 2022). The Netherlands is home to many key players in the semiconductor industry, including ASML which provides equipment for chip manufacturing, NXP which designs chips, and STMicroelectronics which focuses on manufacturing and design. The Netherlands contributes to almost a third of Europe's exports of equipment in semiconductor production, and half of Europe's equipment exports for wafer fabrication. Additionally, Dutch company ASML has a monopoly on EUV lithography production, essential to the production of chips smaller than 7 nanometers, which only Taiwan and South Korea are capable of producing thanks to ASML technology (Kan Ji, 2023).

European Union's Position on the Supply Chain

It is important to consider the general function of the global semiconductor value chain to better understand the European Union's position in comparison to other countries. The global semiconductor value chain is often characterized by many chokepoints and critical inter-dependencies among countries, making it nearly impossible for one sole country to be a self-sufficient semiconductor producer. These chokepoints are determined by the various resources needed in each step a semiconductor chip must go through in the supply chain, which can be seen in **Figure 4** and **Figure 5**. Although the European Union is highly involved in the global semiconductor value chain, is not a dominant final semiconductor producer.

Europe accounts for around 10% of global semiconductor production and primarily focuses on larger, trailing-edge chips with a manufacturing process at 22 nanometers and above (**Figure 6**) The production of cutting-edge chips, ranging from 2 to 7 nanometers, is currently limited to a few companies in East Asia such as TSMC in Taiwan and Samsung in South Korea. That being said, Europe does hold a crucial position in the supply chain as the sole producer of the necessary equipment for manufacturing these cutting-edge nanochips chips, with ASML in the Netherlands leading the way. Companies such as EPFL in Switzerland and Si-Mat in Germany also produce crystal-growing furnaces and machining tools to produce wafers, which they export to countries like China, which has very limited access to them (Kahn, 2021).

Figure 6: Global Semiconductor Market Shares

Source: Center for Security and Technology and Semiconductor Industry Association (2021).

Over time, The European Union's share of global chip revenues has declined from 20% in the 1990s to 10% today. Without prompt and substantial investments, the European Union's global market share is projected to dip below 5%. This decline would significantly threaten Europe's industrial competitiveness and technological autonomy (Ciani, 2022). That being said, measures have been put in place by the European Commission to strengthen Europe's position in the semiconductor manufacturing sector.

European Union's Current Response

In light of the recent semiconductor shortage, The European Union has developed a plan to become more autonomous and competitive as a player in the global league of semiconductor manufacturing. One of the ways the European Union plans to do this is with the help of the European [Chips Act](#) passed by the European Commission in February of 2022. The proposed act aims to mobilize €43 billion in 'policy-driven investment' for the EU's semiconductor sector by 2030 (Van Wieringen, 2022). This comprehensive plan will ultimately address supply disruptions, bolster, and expand production and innovation across the entire semiconductor value chain. If implemented effectively, the Chips Act will help reinforce the European Union's technological leadership, practical applications, and digital sovereignty in the semiconductor industry.

Additionally, The European Union has seen support from companies such as Intel, which is seeking to invest in the EU to create a next-generation European chip ecosystem and address the global need for a more balanced and resilient supply chain. On June 19, 2023, Intel announced its plans for an initial investment exceeding 33 billion euros, to construct a state-of-the-art semiconductor fabrication mega-site in Germany, which is expected to begin construction in 2027 (Intel, 2023). Additionally, Intel plans to establish new (R&D) and fabless design hubs in France and expand capacities in R&D, manufacturing, foundry services, and back-end production in Ireland, Italy, Poland, and Spain. Intel and the European Commission's proposed support to Europe will inevitably increase sustainable semiconductor production in the upcoming years.

Key Players

The interest in semiconductors has increased significantly in recent years, given their importance for the functioning of modern technology and their subsequent contribution to the economy. “World market capitalization of semiconductor companies grew from €438 billion in 2005 to over €2.5 trillion in 2021, with an average yearly increase of over 30% in the last five years, and a record upsurge of 53 % in 2021 as compared to 2020” (Ciani, 2022). Some of the top European companies responsible for that growth include the following listed below, according to 2023 information from [Yahoo Finance](#). **Figure 7** visualizes a comparison between the various companies' market caps.

1. *ASML*: Located in the Netherlands, ASML is the leading company in the European semiconductor market with a market capitalization of \$279.24 billion, and 37,704 full-time employees. ASML specializes in manufacturing EUV lithography technology, which is essential to the production of chips smaller than 7 nanometers. Some of their main clients are TSMC in Taiwan and Samsung in South Korea.
2. *NXP Semiconductors*: Located in the Netherlands, NXP is the second largest semiconductor company in Europe with a market cap of \$54.29 billion and 34,500 full-time employees. NXP's main focus is designing chips and securing connectivity solutions for embedded applications with the goal of making the globe smarter, safer, and more sustainable. Some of the main products NXP offers are microcontrollers, application processors, communication processors, and wireless connectivity solutions.
3. *Infineon Technologies*: Located in Germany, Infineon is another leader in the European semiconductor industry, with a market cap just shy of \$47.1 billion and 57,217 full-time employees. Infineon provides innovative instrumentation, critical sensor technologies, and Smart Manufacturing/Industry 4.0 software solutions that enhance the productivity and quality of tools, processes, and complete factories.
4. *STMicroelectronics*: STM Electronics is another semiconductor company located in The Netherlands with a market cap of \$43.51 billion and 51,370 full-time employees. STMicroelectronics produces a wide range of products including discrete and standard commodity components, custom and semi-custom devices, and application-specific standard and integrated circuits (ICs).
5. *Nordic Semiconductor*: Nordic Semiconductor is a fabless semiconductor company based in Norway with a market cap of \$23.81 billion and 1,513 full-time employees. Nordic Semiconductor supplies clients throughout the globe with integrated circuits (ICs) designs and related products and services for use in short- and long-range wireless applications.
6. *ASM International*: Based in the Netherlands, ASM is a semiconductor company with a market cap of \$19.31 billion and 4,258 full-time employees. ASM International supplies wafer processing equipment to the leading semiconductor manufacturers all around the world, mostly for the deposition of thin films. They design, manufacture, sell, and service deposition tools to supply customers with advanced technologies to produce semiconductor devices, or integrated circuits.
7. *BE Semiconductor Industries*: Another semiconductor company based in the Netherlands, Be Semiconductor Industries has a market cap of \$7.96 billion and has 1,1682 employees. Their main focus is on developing, manufacturing, marketing, selling, and servicing semiconductor assembly equipment for the semiconductor and electronics industries worldwide.
8. *Soitec*: Soitec is a semiconductor company based in France with a market cap of \$5.32 billion and employs 1,986 associates full-time. Soitec designs and manufactures semiconductor products used in smartphones, computers, IT centers, and data centers in addition to producing electronic components used in cars, connected devices, and industrial and medical equipment.
9. *Technoprobe*: Technoprobe is a semiconductor company based in Italy with a market cap of \$4.18 billion and 2,120 full-time employees. Technoprobe produces electronic circuits in Italy and sells them globally. Some of the products they offer include mechanical interfaces for electrical contacting of hybrid circuits and semiconductor devices and probe cards for testing the operation of chips.

10. *Aixtron*: Aixtron is a semiconductor company based in Germany with a market cap of \$3.51 billion and 974 full-time employees. Aixtron is a semiconductor industry provider of deposition equipment and technology solutions to build components for electronic and optoelectronic applications.

Figure 7: Leading semiconductor companies in Europe in 2023

Source: [Yahoo Finance](#) (2023)

Recommendations

It is evident that Europe's position in the global semiconductor value chain is improving especially in recent years; however, there is still some opportunity for growth. One disadvantage the European Union currently faces is its dependency on suppliers and customers headquartered outside of the EU. Around 80% of suppliers to EU semiconductor firms are outside the EU, (Ciani, 2022). Given the fact that a third of global high-purity silicon (the main metal used in wafer production) exports come from Germany, it is in the EU's best interest to leverage this resource and use it to its advantage when making trade deals with other countries for semiconductor equipment.

Another disadvantage that The European Union faces is its lack of semiconductor fabrication plants, which leads many European producers of semiconductor fabrication machines to find customers elsewhere, mainly in East Asia. One such company is ASML, located in the Netherlands, which is the largest producer of machines capable of manufacturing semiconductor chips smaller than 7 nanometers, selling mainly to Taiwan and South Korea. Because of this, I recommend that Europe invest in establishing more fabrication plants in the EU such as the French-Italian FXM and The Netherlands' NXP to incentivize European producers of semiconductor machines such as ASML to sell to a European customer base. This will give European fabrication plants production capacity for advanced nanochips, increasing their share in the market, which could lead to new trade opportunities and ultimately strengthen Europe's position in the semiconductor market overall.

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